

THE ROLE OF PRINCIPLES AND METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article discusses the characteristics of the principles and methods of teaching English in today's educational system. Also, information about the mechanism of educational methods in the process of teaching English is described.

Key words: functional process, intellectual aspect, professional efficiency, method, method, principles.

Nowadays, the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the teaching and learning of the English language is developing consistently and sustainably in all educational institutions, as well as being widely implemented. As a result, the variety of training rooms in all educational institutions is increasing, creating rich opportunities for students and students, as well as opening wide opportunities for effective teaching and learning. As the number of students learning English is increasing day by day around the world, there is an important issue, resource centers in all educational institutions require the formation of a resource that covers the necessary guide materials for learners based on modern methods. Undoubtedly, it is important in the scientific organization of the lesson, as well as creating an immovable strategic foundation template is the need of the hour, which, in turn, is divided into several principles and methods. The purpose of this is to focus on increasing the effectiveness of the lesson.

The educational process conducted by pedagogues-teachers in the training laboratory with the participation of students based on modern educational methods is a source of cooperation based on two partnerships, and the realization of the expected result in the final part determines the creativity skills of the teacher. A different approach to training is aimed not only at strengthening the thinking potential, but also at the sharp development of the student's skills in the field (speaking, writing, reading, listening). *"The integration of interactive methods with skills is explained by the interesting and complementary nature of the lessons. Ensuring its integrity undoubtedly requires pedagogues - teachers to approach their task with responsibility and skill."*

In today's modern era, we see classes and activities with a creative approach and teaching. In determining the knowledge, abilities, and skills of pedagogues-teachers, the effectiveness of the principles or selected methods in each lesson is determined based on the results of the lesson and the performance of the students during the lesson. So, it is clear from this that it is not limited to the application and introduction of modern pedagogical technologies, but to clearly indicate the purpose of the method, the used method, and the principles in increasing the effectiveness of education. If we look at the content and classification of teaching methods and principles, they are explained as follows:

The principle of teaching.

It is a collaborative summation of ideas, beliefs, and methods of natural learning in the classroom.

Teaching strategy.

A well-defined term plan is a clear teaching pattern to achieve the intended goal.

Teaching method.

A systematic way of doing something. A step-by-step approach to a logical plan. A very effective method. The teaching technique is a creative approach based on specific activity and task implementation of a well-defined work order.

The principle of separate engagement.

In this, the student is required to work separately and alone, the goal is for the student to be able to solve the problem situation independently.

The principle of accurate teaching.

Here it is clearly interpreted from the teacher to tell and show or demonstrate.

An orderly principle.

It is limited, the discussion of the teacher is based on the intended topic with the participation of students.

The principle of cooperation.

Group, team, partnership work and group discussion; relies on a collaborative approach.

Interactive principle.

In this principle, in an interactive classroom, more students speak and the role of the teacher is less. Students are allowed to interact with the teacher and other students.

The principle of creative device.

"Creating students' knowledge skills and understanding the essence of pre-existing skills experience".

The principle and method of the educational strategy mentioned above is a set of general educational components. "These components strengthen the overall integration process in English language teaching, and as a result gradually develop the teaching-training procedures." When determining the professional component skill of each teacher in teaching English, it is determined by his ability to organize the training, the structural strategic principle, and the method principle that can effectively perform the sequential steps. Therefore, there are several principles in the organization of a high-quality lesson, which in their place are the full achievement of the intended goal of the teacher and students. It is definitely impossible to use several methods during training, or to use at least one method in full efficiency is undoubtedly a complicated process. Accordingly, we cannot say which method is too complicated or useful for teachers, rather we believe that the most appropriate method and approach for training is based on the quality and structure of the teachers' own lessons. The optional aspect of learning is intended to help students and improve the effectiveness of the environment. Diversity and flexibility are meaningful features of the classroom environment.

The chain of modern pedagogical technologies, strategies, methods and principles in teaching English is a criterion for organizing interactive classes and the potential for interest is sufficiently developed, as a result of which the positive characteristics of the individual potential of cooperation methods are correspondingly perfected. *"Each method or method selected by the teacher not only increases the effectiveness of the lesson - training, but also increases the student's productivity, which represents the goal of being one step ahead of the teacher's goals"*¹. In increasing the student's scientific potential, it is focused on concretizing the goals and tasks of each principle and ensuring consistency, in which international and national cooperation strengthened the modern teaching strategy of professors and teachers and expanded the principles of experience.

In conclusion, each of the above purposefully used teaching methods helps to reveal some of the student's skills, for example, deductive and inductive learning areas develop the student's internal and external knowledge skills, creative thinking, learning and analysis. So, when the teacher, based on his principle, introduces the methods selected based on the purpose and principle of his planned lesson into the individual or team-style educational form, the overall revitalization, i.e. growth, is gradually strengthened, goes We, pedagogues,

¹ Penny Ur "A Course in Language Teaching: Practice of Theory "Cambridge Teacher Training and Development. 2009.p123

understand very well that we cannot limit ourselves to only one method or method in the English language class, which is a situation that puts the student in a difficult situation. It is necessary to avoid such a model of homogeneity of a teacher-pedagogue and to increase the effectiveness of new competences.

References:

1. Jalolov J. "Methodology of reading English" (textbook) T.- 2012
2. Hoshimov O', Yakubov I. "METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH" (study guide) T.-, Sharq Publishing House. 2013
3. Penny Ur "A Course in Language Teaching: Practice of Theory" Cambridge Teacher Training and Development. 2009
4. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.
5. <https://monster-evo.ru/uz/studentu/metody-priemy-raboty-na-uroke-angliiskogo-yazyka-metody-i-priemy/>

